

An Underwater Image Enhancement Method Based on Artificial Intelligence

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To Cite this Article

Banavat Durga Bhavani & Dr. D. Naga Ravi Kiran (2026). An Underwater Image Enhancement Method Based on Artificial Intelligence. International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 12(SI01), 378-384. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19561879>

Article Info

Received: 02 March 2026; Revised: 01 April 2026; Accepted: 04 April 2026.

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KEYWORDS	ABSTRACT
Image Enhancement, Under Water Image, Artificial Intelligence, Fully Connected Neural Network (FCNN), MSE, PSNR.	Underwater image processing is a dynamic field that has garnered increasing interest due to its critical applications in marine biology, geological explorations and military reconnaissance. Underwater images taken with underwater cameras often experience visual deterioration, including problems like color distortion, diminished contrasts, and blurred details. Such problems were caused by dispersion and refraction of light as they penetrate from rarer to denser media. The scattering of light reduces color contrast. Here we introduce an improved method for under water image enhancement based on the fusion method that is capable to restore accurately underwater images. This paper presents An Underwater Image Enhancement Method Based on Artificial Intelligence. The proposed method is built upon AI framework using Fully Connected Neural Network (FCNN). By using UIEB (underwater image enhancement benchmark) dataset, the described model is trained. The effectiveness and robustness of the real-time algorithm are satisfactory for various underwater images under different conditions. The mean square error (MSE), peak signal to noise ratio (PSNR), and structural similarity (SSIM) evaluation measures are used in this paper. The proposed Fully Convolutional Neural Network model is proved with respect to performance and comparison against several models.

I. INTRODUCTION

Underwater imagery is a good source of information for gaining insight into marine organisms, detecting rich cultural heritage underwater, and studying hydrothermal vents on the seafloor. Currently, underwater images can be obtained with optical cameras and underwater techniques such as laser scanning,

distance selective transmission and polarised light [1]. However, raw underwater images cannot be directly exploited due to effects of the water medium. Therefore, there are various pre processing methods for underwater image enhancement.

Underwater image enhancement and detection have become vital research areas due to their importance in

marine exploration, ecological monitoring, underwater archaeology, and industrial applications like oil and gas exploration [2]. Nonetheless, underwater imaging confronts unique obstacles, including light absorption, scattering, color distortion, backscatter from suspended particles, and low contrast and resolution. The harsh underwater environment, characterized by high pressure, darkness, and temperature variations, complicates these issues, particularly with increasing depth. Historically, early underwater imaging relied on conventional photography, but visibility issues and color degradation hindered effectiveness.

Over the past few decades, researchers and experts have devoted substantial efforts to underwater image enhancement. Various methods can be categorized as physical model based, non-physical model-based, and data-driven approaches [3]. Physical model-based methods treat underwater image enhancement as an inverse problem and rely on estimating the parameters of the image formation model to obtain clear underwater images.

Many methods developed to overcome the challenge of the low resolution of underwater images. Nevertheless, some inherent limitations such as artifacts, blurring, and noise, have highlighted the importance of developing methods and strategies for underwater photography and consequently image processing. The image improvement process includes a range of technologies such as filters, frameworks, and algorithms to retain image sharpness, which is commonly harmed by noise, blur, and artifacts [4]. Many application-oriented areas benefit greatly from digital image processing. Image processing is used in a variety of applications, including military, biometrics, robotics, genetics, radar images, satellite images, medical images, and more. If the image shifts from a normal to an aberrant shape, it suggests that there are fluctuations in brightness, contrast level, resolution, and so on.

To address these challenges, Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based underwater image enhancement methods have emerged as powerful solutions. AI techniques, particularly those from Deep Learning and Computer Vision, are widely used to automatically learn complex mappings between degraded underwater images and their enhanced counterparts. Unlike traditional methods that rely on handcrafted filters or physical models, AI-based approaches can adaptively improve image

quality by learning from large datasets. The benefits of AI-based underwater image enhancement include improved visual quality, better feature extraction for downstream tasks, and real-time processing capabilities when deployed on optimized hardware [5]. These improvements are crucial for applications like underwater surveillance, marine biodiversity monitoring, and autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs). Therefore, this paper presents An Underwater Image Enhancement Method based on Artificial Intelligence.

The rest of the Paper is organized as follows: Section II includes literature reviews, Section III includes An Underwater Image Enhancement Method based on Artificial Intelligence, Section IV includes results analysis, and Section V concludes the paper.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

In [6] first optimize the main network framework for the Water-net baseline model by selecting two convolutional blocks that differ only in the number of channels to be learned. For fusion, three different and more advantageous preprocessing methods are selected and increase the AquaBlend ConvModule (ABCM) enhancement module to enhance output quality while preventing overfitting. The improved model shows intentional performance on the full reference metrics, which is significantly improved compared to the baseline model, and the effectiveness of our method is verified in experiments on diverse underwater datasets.

In [7] proposed algorithm applies Single Image Dehazing to resolve the issue related to underwater image degradation. Firstly, calculation of dark channel to give low intensity value image is performed followed by finding the atmospheric light for underwater images. Real time monitoring and surveillance in an underwater domain are the potential application areas of this method. In [8] discussed to improve underwater image, color balance and fusion are used. The author took a single underwater shot and used multiple variations of the same input image to apply gamma and white balance modifications. These two photos are combined into a single output image via multiscale fusion. This method restores faded features and edges with a single input, but it does not restore colors or completely remove haze.

In [9] presented a method for preserving hue in underwater colour images The HSI (Hue Saturation

Intensity) and HSV (Hue Saturation and Value) colour models were addressed using wavelet domain filtering and boundary histogram stretching methods, respectively. By preserving the hue components, this method improves image quality in terms of contrast, color rendering, uneven lighting, and noise reduction. In [10] described a method for stretching RGB and HSV color models (hue, saturation, value) has been developed to improve underwater image quality. To improve contrast, the author used the Rayleigh distribution to remove less than 0.2 percent and more than 99.8 percent of the histogram intensity and increase the remaining intensity across the dynamic range. This issue will be resolved with images that were either too dark or too bright.

In [11] described by used a splitter to capture the image in different orientations, the above method is used to rectify the degradation of an underwater photograph. The main degrading effect is generated by light partial polarization, according to this method. The software technique, on the other hand, does not require specialist hardware and instead seeks to reproduce the image using a number of image processing approaches.

III. AN UNDERWATER IMAGE ENHANCEMENT METHOD

The block diagram of An Underwater Image Enhancement Method based on Artificial Intelligence is shown in Figure 1. The UIEB (underwater image enhancement benchmark) dataset consists of unprocessed underwater images and their corresponding pseudo-reference images, which serve as a benchmark for real-world underwater image enhancement. The UIEB dataset provides the benefit of a variety of underwater sceneries, by exhibiting a broad spectrum of image content, image resolutions, and quality degradation characteristics and a substantial number of underwater images and associated high-quality reference images. The UIEB dataset comprises of two subsets: one consisting of 890 raw underwater images and their corresponding high-quality reference images, while the other subset contains 60 challenging underwater images.

The enhancement considers an important preprocessing operation for further processing of the image whereby, some challenges such as high dimension, good resolution, and high density of unwanted noises in underwater images increase the time

of processing and computational complexity.

In addition, the classical gray world algorithm assumed that the mean reflectance of the scene is achromatic, and one estimated the color distribution of the light source by averaging each channel separately. This strategy performs well in removing color deviation. However, when it is directly applied to the underwater images, a certain degree of artifacts will be introduced due to over compensation, especially for serious color deviation area. In order to avoid this problem, it is necessary to compensate the color loss before applying this strategy.

Figure 1. Block diagram of Underwater Image Enhancement Method based on AI

High frequency components in underwater images are suppressed during color balancing. Guided filters facilitates retaining high frequency components, and is considered to be one of the fastest and efficient edge preserving and smoothing filters. We apply fast guided filter on simplest color balanced image.

Histogram equalization is the most commonly employed technique to boost the contrast and improve

the visibility of the undersea image. Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) is done to increase the image contrast which is achieved by extending the intensity range of the image and spreading out the frequently occurring intensity levels and to reduce the contrast's over-amplification. The image is divided into small blocks, and histogram equalization is applied to each block separately to enhance its contrast. Then, based on the cumulative distribution function of each block, the pixel values are redistributed while ensuring that the maximum slope of the function is limited.

A Fully Convolutional Neural Network (FCNN) is a deep learning architecture specifically designed to process images of any size by using only convolutional layers (no fully connected layers). There are 4 layers in this architecture. Input Layer: The degraded underwater image is fed into the network. Feature Extraction: Convolutional layers extract features like edges, textures, and color variations. Non-linear Mapping: Multiple layers learn the transformation from low-quality to high-quality image. Reconstruction Layer: Final convolutional layers reconstruct the enhanced image. In underwater image enhancement, FCNNs are highly effective because they perform pixel-wise prediction, making them ideal for restoring degraded images.

FCNN-based methods provide a powerful and flexible solution for underwater image enhancement. By leveraging Deep Learning and Computer Vision, they significantly improve visual quality and enable better performance in underwater imaging applications. The resulting image has been enhanced, noise has been reduced, edges have been preserved, and colors have been restored. The mean square error (MSE), peak signal to noise ratio (PSNR), and structural similarity (SSIM) evaluation measures are used in this paper.

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

This section presents performance of described Underwater Image Enhancement Method based on Artificial Intelligence. By using UIEB (underwater image enhancement benchmark) dataset, the described model is trained. The UIEB dataset comprises of two subsets: one consisting of 890 raw underwater images and their corresponding high-quality reference images. The mean square error (MSE), peak signal to noise ratio (PSNR),

and structural similarity (SSIM) evaluation measures are used in this paper.

In underwater image enhancement, the **Mean Squared Error (MSE)** is a quantitative metric used to measure the pixel-level difference between an enhanced image and a ground-truth (reference) image. It calculates the average of the squares of the errors—that is, the average squared difference between the estimated values (enhanced image pixels) and the actual values (reference image pixels).

$$MSE = \frac{1}{WH} \sum_{i=0}^{H-1} \sum_{j=0}^{W-1} (I_{ref}(i,j) - I_{out}(i,j))^2 \quad (1)$$

Where, W and H are denotes the width and height of image, $I_{ref}(i,j)$ is Pixel value of the reference (ground truth) image at coordinates, $I_{out}(i,j)$ Pixel value of the enhanced (output) image at coordinates.

Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR): Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) is a mathematical measurement of image quality. It is based on the difference in pixels between two images. The SNR measurement is an estimate of the improved image quality compared to the original image. PSNR is determined according to the following equation:

$$PSNR = 10 \log_{10} \left[\frac{R^2}{MSE} \right] \quad (2)$$

Signal strength is taken into account by PSNR. The value was used to assess the image's quality. R indicates the image's greatest fluctuation or value.

SSIM is a method for estimating the perceived quality of digital television and cinematic pictures, as well as other types of digital pictures and videos. SSIM is used to measure the similarity between two images. The SSIM index is a complete reference metric; in other words, the measurement or estimation of image quality is based on an uncompressed or distortion-free first image as a reference.

$$SSIM(x,y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + C_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + C_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + C_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + C_2)} \quad (3)$$

Where, x,y are The enhanced image and the reference image, respectively. σ denotes the variance, μ denotes mean of image. C_1 and C_2 denotes small constants.

Table 1 shows the comparative performance analysis of described model Underwater Image Enhancement Method based on AI (FCNN), Underwater Image Enhancement using support vector machine (SVM) and convolutional neural network (CNN) in terms of MSE, PSNR and SSIM.

Table 1. Comparative performance analysis

Models	MSE	PSNR	SSIM
SVM	56.7	21.2	0.7
CNN	44.3	26.4	0.81
FCNN	27.2	32.7	0.95

Figure 2 shows the comparative performance analysis of MSE and PSNR value for described Underwater Image Enhancement Method based on AI (FCNN), Underwater Image Enhancement using SVM and CNN. Where x-axis represents the models and y-axis represents the parameter value. From figure it is observed that, MSE of described model is very less and PSNR of described model is high compared with other models.

Figure 2. Comparative analysis related to MSE and PSNR

Figure 3 represents the comparative graphical analysis of SSIM parameter for described Underwater Image Enhancement Method based on AI (FCNN), Underwater Image Enhancement using SVM and CNN, in which the x-axis represents the models and y-axis represents the parameter value. SSIM value of described model is very high compared to other models.

Figure 3. Comparative analysis related to SSIM

The collected images in this paper are sampled in Figure 4 and their respective enhanced images are represented in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Raw input images

Figure 5. Enhanced images

According to the findings, An Underwater Image Enhancement Method based on Artificial Intelligence is highly efficient in terms of performance parameters. MSE of described model is very less and PSNR of described model is high compared with other models. SSIM value of described model is very high. The proposed methods provide quite satisfactory underwater images, according to the overall results.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, An Underwater Image Enhancement Method based on Artificial Intelligence is described. The

application of Artificial Intelligence techniques in underwater image enhancement has exhibited remarkable advancements, transcending the limitations posed by challenging underwater conditions. By using UIEB (underwater image enhancement benchmark) dataset, the described model is trained. The UIEB dataset comprises of two subsets: one consisting of 890 raw underwater images and their corresponding high-quality reference images. FCNN-based methods provide a powerful and flexible solution for underwater image enhancement. The mean square error (MSE), peak signal to noise ratio (PSNR), and structural similarity (SSIM) evaluation measures are used in this paper. According to the findings, An Underwater Image Enhancement Method based on Artificial Intelligence is highly efficient in terms of performance parameters. MSE of described model is very less and PSNR of described model is high compared with other models. SSIM value of described model is very high. The proposed methods provide quite satisfactory underwater images, according to the overall results.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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